

The Relevance of Applying Universal Education Theory and Other Educational Theories in The 21st Century

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Abstract:

The study adopted explanatory research design, cross-sectional survey as research strategy, qualitative research approach, the population were 10 writers, the data was acquired through primary source, the procedure of acquiring data was to examine what other writers had written concerning the topic under study. The sampling design were survey of research papers published by academic journals and papers published at various websites. The objectives of the study were achieved and the problem statement was Relevance of applying Universal Education Theory and other educational theories in the 21st century. The introduction was brief of history of education. The study found out significance of education, the various kinds of educational theories, impact of educational theories, how to apply educational theories, causes of students' poor performance in academics, implication of behavioral, the formula of Universal Education (UE), cognitive theories; problems teachers face in the classrooms. The study generalized that application of universal education theory and other educational theories were important in the 21st century. The study motivated teachers to study learning theories and used them for the benefits of their students.

Keywords: Universal Education Theory, Educational Theories, Educational theories in the 21st century, applying educational theories,

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BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Introduction

Education is derived from the Latin word called "educatio" meaning "breeding," "bringing up," or "rearing".

During prehistory era, adults trained young people to acquire knowledge and skills in their societies. This was possible through orals, imitation. Through storytelling, knowledge, values and skills were passed from one generation to future generation. Formal education developed when cultures extend knowledge beyond skills and was readable through imitation. At the time of Mind Kingdom schools were established in Egypt. Plato founded Seminary in Athens and it was the first Seminary in Europe. The Alexandria city in Egypt was founded in 330 BCE and became the center for intellectuals of Ancient Greece. Alexandria Library was formed in the 3rd century (History of education,n.d).

Education is the act of imparting knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, habits and training to become more advanced. Education was established as a medium to transfer cultural heritage from one generation to future generation. Education involves new ideas likes liberation of scholars, critical thinking, skills for modern society, empathy and vocational skills. Formal education occurs in classroom and is structured by curriculum, objectives and learning is controlled by a teacher. In many regions formal education is mandatory to people in a country to attain to a certain stage. Formal education is categorized into stages such as kindergarten, primary school and secondly school. The various ways of imparting knowledge are teaching, training, storytelling, discussion and research. This is called pedagogy. Education is assisted by different philosophies, theories and emperical research agendas. The steps for education reforms are developing quality education and solving problems future generation. Government and United Nations value the right approach to education. (Education,n.d).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the history of education.
- To find out various kinds of educational theories.
- To find out impact of educational theories.
- To find out the significance of education.
- To find out implications of behavioral and cognitive theories.
- To find out to apply educational theories.
- To find out the history of educational theories.
- To find out causes of students' poor performance in academics.
- To find out the problems teachers face in the classrooms.

BRIEF HISTORY OF EDUCATIONAL THEORIES

In 1890s before psychology was accepted as experimental science, learning was considered but in 1910 psychologists were excited by learning concept and learning theories. Between 1930s and 1940s were known as golden age of learning theory and learning was believed to be the heart and soul of psychology. The theorists were not able settle their differences of opinion. Psychologists thought that the differences were matter of opinion couple with a little

of empirical evidence and generated debate over basic issues. Around 1960 new measures and phenomena were found that made psychologists to stop arguing basic issues.

SIGNIFICANCE OF EDUCATION

It is hard to search for job in times of economic crisis but one has to compete with hundreds of candidates for a vacant position. People who have low educational background get job with poor salary. Literates with high qualifications get prestigious work and earn good salary. Scholars who prefer to be ahead of job-seekers should study hard to get high qualification. We ought to devote much time to academic work in order to acquire in-depth knowledge. Through this, we will enjoy life in the future. The qualification of a person market for job instead of struggling with people for job. Employers are seeking for people who are competent. The educational system is designed to enable us to obtain and develop critical and logical thinking and to live independent life. When Children reach adult stage, they encountered problems such as paying students loans, searching for a job, buy a car; catering for family members. Through education, we can deal with the above mentioned problems. Scholars who are highly educated have opportunities to enjoy life. While people with low education struggle to enjoy life. Through this, they help to decrease poverty in a society. Education enables a country to grow economically because education is all about acquiring knowledge and applying them wisely and use the knowledge to improve people's lives. Education helps us to be unique in a society. Before we can experience happiness in life, we ought to be highly educated and would help us to get good job. It makes people to honor us and motives us to strive to climb academic ladder. People can provide for themselves and have the resources to look after their families. It gives us hope and boldness to move forward in life. It enables us to improve upon our communication skills by learning how to read, write, speak and listen. It assists to meet basic jobs qualifications, promotes gender equality and empower girls and women. It has decreased the rate of teenage pregnancy by 6 percent and gives women power to rule their own children and reduces child mortality rates.

THESIS STATEMENT: The problem statement was "Relevance of applying universal education theory and other educational theories in the 21st century. The study found out the importance of education, development of various kinds of educational theories, impact of educational theories, implications of behavioral, the formula of Universal Education (UE), cognitive theories, how to use educational theories, causes of students' poor performance in academics, problems teachers face in the classrooms and the history of educational theories.

DEVELOPMENT OF VARIOUS KINDS OF EDUCATIONAL THEORIES

Universal Education Theory: This theory was established by Dr. Rejaul Abedin in 2019. According to his theory man should change in their lifestyle and exhibit good morals both personal and academic lives. The theory helps man to develop values and enables students to involve in academic program. This will benefit the entire training and develop individuals, students in academic program, comprising of people in diverse moral programs and personal study could be beneficial for moral development. Dr. Rejaul Abedin's "UE" or Universal Education Theory if applies properly with respect to moral development individual trainees and societies will benefit a lot.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FORMULA OF UNIVERSAL EDUCATION THEORY

The formula of Universal education is: $UE=[Hv+[EA+EsT]+MR]-Ie$

UE= Universal Education/ Global Education.

Hv= Individual persons who needs value addition.

EA= Education through Academics.

EsT= Self-learning education and Talent acquired from Almighty God.

MR= Moral training receive through Religion.

Ie= Man setting himself apart for what is morally right / (Eradication of Individual Evils).

Behaviorism Theory: This means learners ability to observe what is happening in their environment and study through systematic process. This theory originated in the early 1900s and was accepted in the 20th century. The purpose of learning is similar to "drill and practice programs" The behaviourists focus on changes in behavior.

IMPLICATIONS OF BEHAVIORAL THEORIES

Well-organized environment assists learning to happen and teachers ought to prepare the environment that will compel students to learn. Teachers must advice students to learn what they have been taught. This challenges them to learn hard. Teachers should give awards to good students and should award those who exhibit good behavior towards learning. However, to fight against bad behavior teachers should punish students who show such behavior. Teachers must be aware that developing teaching as a profession has a lot of advantages like helping students to learn, broaden their knowledge; improving their personal lives

Cognitivism theory: That is learning depends on internal and external factors. This theory was established between 1970s and 1980s and indicated that learners were not only received information; they were sense-makers and not recording given information but interpret it.

Constructivism theory: This implies students should develop base on their past so that we can create new ideas.

Cognitive psychology: This theory was developed in 1950s and the idea was to condemn the theory of behaviourism. Cognitive psychology regards people as those who process information and concerns about complex mental phenomena which behaviourists have overlooked. Learning is a process of acquiring knowledge and the learner is known as information processor where the learner absorbs the information.

IMPLICATIONS OF COGNITIVE THEORY

Teachers must put together teaching materials in a manner that will enable students to acquire ideas they possess. They ought to adopt different teaching methods. Through this, students get ideas from different angles and teachers should be role models to students. They must give students exercises to do in class and exercises urges them to learn hard. This enables them to be academically active. Course and topics should be divided into sub points which students to understand.

Humanism: This concern learners concentration on academic work instead of method.

DEVELOPMENTAL THEORY

This theory was developed by Jean Piaget. He concentrated on the development of children 's understanding. He was able to do this through observation. His focus was to find out how children's minds worked and developed.

TRANSFORMATIVE THEORY: This theory deals with adult learners and says that new information can change our perceptions on worldviews when life experience and knowledge are compared with critical reflection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of writers have written articles about educational theories which have contributed to the progress of education. However, notwithstanding the views of the writers the study investigated into "Relevance of applying universal education theory and other educational theories in the 21st century". Because of this, the study finds out writers who have written about the subject under study. In 2019 Dr. Rejaul Abedin wrote an article entitled "Implementation of universal education theory in global education system" This theory improves the life of man, teams and societies and fight against evil. He said moral education was vital to everybody in all sphere of life and moral lessons should be taught in schools, colleges, Universities, Vocational Schools; Madrasas. It is the responsibilities of parents to impact moral values to their children so that they could develop moral qualities like humility, integrity, truthfulness, courtney, tolerance; sacrifices. This will help them to develop positive attitude towards future generation which would enable them to fight against evil. Morality is about knowing what is good and what is bad In reference to (Wikipedia,n.d) an article written entitled "learning theory" which defines learning as how students receive, process and retain knowledge during learning. Cognitive, emotional, environmental influence and experience count in terms of understanding. Behaviorists consider learning as aspect of condition and promotes rewards and aim at education. Those who believe in cognitive theory see learning as transformation of behavior to narrow and study the scholars rather than their environment. With respect to the views of the above writers, the study found out significance of education, development of various kinds of educational theories, impact of educational theories, how to adopt educational theories, implications of behavioral, the formula of Universal Education (UE) Theory and cognitive theories, the history of education and the history of educational theories.

IMPACT OF EDUCATIONAL THEORIES

Educational theories have impact on teachers approach to instructions and classroom governance. Apply theories properly spell out the difference between effective classroom experience and infective one. Educational theories give students structure, comfortable and steady stimuli. They assist educators, administers, students and parents to rely on goals and results. They enable teachers to make choice about how to teach in a manner that will benefits their students. They help to understand how and what a person study. They enable Colleges and testing films to know the kind of education a student received. They permit students to suggest how the class should be managed. They specify how collaboration will occur in a classroom. They help to improve upon teaching and determine the best theory for teaching. They enable scholars to improve upon their academic work. They provide basis for criticizing the accuracy and essence of beliefs. They give basic glues about hard process of learning. Connectivism and Andragogy theories assist to deal with specific population of students. They help to know how students study and deal with academic issues. They provide insight about how information is processed, how knowledge is discovered and how learning happen. Learning designers can use these structures in combination with different studies and scholars have to plan about selecting the right method of teaching.

HOW TO APPLY EDUCATIONAL THEORIES

Teachers should find way to teach to educational theories in their classroom. They have to focus on getting a "well-rounded education" and study the types of teaching methods and classroom management. They ought to be familiar with learning theories in order to have control over their courses. Through understand of educational theories, they can bring many students together. They should adopt different learning styles in order to enhance effective teaching. With behaviourism theory, teachers should use the "Law of Effect" through engaging students in activities that will motivate them academically.

CAUSES OF STUDENTS POOR PERFORMANCE IN ACADEMICS

Sloughness: A lot of students feel lazy and sluggish to devote their time for personal studies. They spend much of their time on necessary things at the expense of committing themselves to studies. They rush to study when examination is around the corner.

Timetable: A student who does not have timetable is bound to fail in academics. Sad to say many students do not have timetable.

Insufficient: This common among students of 21st century. Many students do not have time for their books. It takes sacrifices for students to come out with flying colors.

Finance: Lack of money to buy textbooks and other study materials are the results of poor performance in academics.

Study materials: Students who do not have money to buy study materials and do not excel in academic. Many students do not pass SSCE, GCE and other examinations because of study material. Students who have sufficient study materials stand in better position to excel than those who do not have.

Broken home: This is one of the factors which causes poor academic performance. Broken home can create depression; retire progress.

Doubt: Doubt creates fear among students who are on the way to success. Doubt conquers belief, desire for success and doubter is a loser.

Discouragement: Discouraged students will definitely fail and discourage comes in when they are facing problems.

PROBLEMS TEACHERS ENCOUNTER IN THE CLASSROOM

A lot young people do not value education and students due to lack of motivation fail to develop their potentials.; they become burden to teachers. Teachers should find a way to know what their students are interested in and assist them to develop their talents. Many students are saucy to teachers in schools which is common in the entire country. Young people portray disrespectful behavior to teachers especially on television and in movies. Parental cooperation with teachers enable students to succeed in academics. Teachers find it hard to get parents involve because they lack the skills. Teachers normally found cell phone in the classrooms. The phones make noise when they are ringing or vibrating and students text messages to their friends. These actions are hindrances to academic success. Many students do not go to bed on time and cannot focus when a teacher is teaching. These sleeping students are not able to understand the lesson.

METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter covers research design, research approach, research strategy, population, sampling design, the source of data collection and the method of data collection. The research approach used was explanatory research design. Through this, study achieved the objectives

of the study. The study used qualitative research approach. Because the study was interested in relevance of applying educational theories. The research strategy used was cross-sectional survey where the study examined papers published by academic journals and papers published at various websites. The population of the study, sampling design, the source of data collection and the method of data collection were thoroughly examined.

SAMPLING DESIGN: The study considered writers' views about the topic under study.

POPULATION OF STUDY: The population of the study were 10 authors.

SOURCE OF DATA COLLECTION: The source of collecting data for the study was primary source.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION: The method of collecting data for the study was research.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study found out during prehistory era adults trained young people to acquire knowledge and skills in their societies. Through education, knowledge was transmitted from one generation to another. Scholars who were highly learned got good job and received good salary. The credentials of a person will found job for him or her. In 1890s before was accepted as experimental science learning played major role. Between 1930s and 1940s were known as golden age of learning theory and learning was regarded as the heart and soul of psychology. Teachers must have adopted method to apply educational theories in their classrooms. Educational theories had impact on teachers' approach to instructions and classroom management.

CONCLUSION

The study found that learning theories had influenced teaching as a profession and the academic of students. Because of this, the study generalized that educational theories were relevant in the 21st century.

RECOMMENDATION

Study

Teachers must do their best to study the various kinds of educational theories and use the type that will suit his or her class, in terms understanding morality, religious ethics and practices such values in each and every sphere of their personal life.

Ministry of education

The ministry of education ought to create platform to teach teachers to know and understand the various educational theories and how to apply them to the benefits of students.

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